

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№7

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golischeva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

Elektron nashr. 480 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-iyulda ruxsat etildi.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Suv tarkibining wireless waterlight qurilmasi ishlashiga ta'siri va iqtisodiy samaradorligini matematik model asosida tahlil qilish.....	14
Kungiratbay Sharipov, Ma'ruf Nurmanov	
O'zbekistonda aholi ish bilan bandligini oshirishda davlatning roli	20
Juraqulov Baxrimurod Ilxomovich	
BIM texnologiyasi: zamonaviy qurilish sohasida samaradorlik va shaffoflik omili	26
Usmonov F.B., Rajabova A.Sh.	
Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarida marketing faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish metodologiyasini takomillashtirish	31
Yuldashov Isomiddin Sidiqov	
Korxonada iqtisodiy barqarorligini ta'minlashda diversifikatsiya strategiyasining roli.....	35
Alimatova Shoxsanam Abdumalik qizi	
Модели совместного развития человеческого капитала и искусственного интеллекта в цифровую эпоху	40
Явкачев Шохзод Зайниддин углы	
Navigating sustainable development: management challenges and solutions in the oil and gas sector	49
Kudratkhodjaeva Ziyoda Kamol kizi	
Banklarda moliyaviy barqarorlikning nazariy asoslari.....	56
Djalilov G'ayrat Qaxramanovich	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda turizm industriyasidan foydalanishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribalari	66
Abdulxakimov Zuxrali Tursunaliyevich	
O'zbekistonda barqaror davlat qarzi siyosatini shakllantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	71
Sayfutdinov Xasanboy Dilshodovich	
Международный опыт сельскохозяйственного налогообложения и возможности его применения в узбекистане.....	76
Salimov Sherzod Baxtiyorovich	
Economic analysis and development strategy of the composites market in the regions of Uzbekistan	81
S.S.Sidiqov, A.A.G'ulomov, B.R.Tillayeva	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida moliyaviy mustaqillikning kutilayotgan istiqbollari va hozirgi natijalari.....	88
Muxamedov Ravshan Zafarovich	
Elektron tijoratni soliqqa tortish mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	93
Homidov Baxtiyor Rahimberdievich	
Investitsion jozibadorlik konsepsiyasi va uning strategik ahamiyati.....	99
Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li	
Beomeditsina signallarini xaar veyvletlari va bo'lak veyvletlari yordamida raqamli ishlash	105
Uraqov Shokir Ulashovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini moliyalashtirishning ahamiyati, tartibi va takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	112
Istamova Sojida Kaxarovna	
The role of all kinds of transports (road, rail, air, and water) in the modern enhancement of tourism logistics in Uzbekistan	117
Egamberdiyeva Yulduz, Turdiyeva Maftuna	
Sanoat korxonalarida kapitalarini samaradorligini oshirishning baholashning zamonaviy usullarining xususiyatlarida nazariy va amaliy farovonlik sari	126
Muradov Botir Xayat	
Инструменты планирования урбанизации: методика анализа планового распределения средств в программе «обод махалля» на основе балльной оценки	136
Салимова Юлдуз Исаковна	
Socio-economic aspects and contemporary theories of higher education finance	141
Karlibaeva Gulshat	

Transformatsiya jarayonida innovatsion bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	147
Absamatov Anvar Ergashovich	
Перспективы цифрового развития сектора материального производства.....	153
С. И. Протасеня, Г. Ж. Аллаева	
«Sustainable logistics practices. Minimizing carbon emissions in global supply chains»	161
Suleymonova Ezoza, Alimova Bonu	
Analyzing the need for Tourism logistics development in Uzbekistan	169
Nigmatova Malika	
Management strategies for sustainable tourism development in emerging destinations (a case study of Samarkand, Issyk-kul, and Khiva).....	177
Sabina Uroкова	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida turizm sohasini strategik rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy asoslari va ularning qo'llanilishi.....	184
Daminova Barno Esanovna	
Опыт турции в управлении миграционными кризисами	189
Бегматов Хусанбек	
Bulutli texnologiyalar orqali korxonalar buxgalteriya tizimini raqamlashtirish va samaradorlikka erishish.....	193
Soibov Nozimbek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Barqaror rivojlanish doirasida jismoniy shaxslarni kreditlash tizimini isloh qilishning institutsonal asoslari.....	197
Xalekeyeva Zoya Pirniyazovna, Akmal Abdurahmonov Nurmamatovich	
Moliyaviy outsorsing xizmatlari bozori rivojlanishini takomillashtirishning swot tahliliga asoslangan innovatsion mexanizmlari	202
San'atbek Komilovich Salayev, Umidbek Komiljanovich Babajanov	
Transformatsiya jarayonlari sharoitida iqtisodiyot tizimi faoliyati va prognozlashning nazariy asoslari	214
Alimov Fazliddin Xalimovich	
Пути совершенствования подхода к финансированию проектов, реализуемых на принципах промышленной кооперации.....	220
Котов В.А., Шадиева Д.Х.	
Yuksalish salohiyatini yuksaltirishda boshqaruv xodimlari qobiliyatidan foydalanish masalalar	225
Ayubxon Qutbiddinov Bosit o'g'li	
Bank xizmatlari ommabopligini oshirish yo'llari.....	228
Kasimova Muxlisa Anvar qizi	
Chemical industry in Uzbekistan: challenges and development	235
Kudaynazarova Dilnaz Koshkarbaevna	
Samarqand viloyatida tabiiy turistik resurslardan samarali foydalanish usullarini takomillashtirish orqali bandligini oshirish imkoniyatlari.....	240
Rabbimov Muhriddin Musoqul o'g'li	
Globalashuv sharoitida ekologik xavflarni kamaytirishda yashil iqtisodiyotning ahamiyati.....	246
Xolbekova Feruzaxon Rasulovna	
Qibray tumanining 2021–2023-yillarda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish holati.....	249
Siddikov Alisher Ismoilovich	
Davlat xaridlari tizimida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish: xalqaro tajribalar tahlili	253
Majidov Nizom Baxramovich	
Oilaviy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi.....	259
Ermatov Nosir Tohirovich	
Aholi farovonligi darajasiga ta'sir etuvchi ko'rsatkichlarni ekonometrik baholash	265
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna, Allamurodova Zuxra Alibekovna	
Сектор услуг как стратегический фактор структурной трансформации экономики Узбекистана.....	272
Кадыров Абдурашид Маджидович, Ахмедиева Алия Тохтаровна	
O'zbekistonda valyuta kursini shakllanish holati prognozlari.....	280
Samandarov Zuxriddin Raup o'g'li	

Проблемы бухгалтерского учета в условиях цифровизации экономики.....	288
Абдуллаев Абдурауф	
Raqamli texnologiyalar sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarida iqtisodiy resurslardan samarali foydalanish strategiyalari.....	299
Kuldoshev Lazizjon Sharifovich	
Davlat boshqaruvi organlarining strategik rejalarini ishlab chiqish bo'yicha xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	303
Dilshod Pulatov, Xamidaxon Akbarova, Dildora Mirzaeva	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy xavfsizligi ta'minlash	310
Mamatov Sardor Axmatjonovich, Mavlanov Nuriddin Boyqobilovich, Sattarov Nodirjon Absalomovich	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishda halol standartlarini qo'llashning nazariy, uslubiy va konseptual asoslari	315
Azizova Saodat Xabibulloyevna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini moliyalashtirish bo'yicha yevropa tajribasi.....	320
Karlibaeva Gulshat	
Iqtisodiy konsentratsiyalarning sog'lom raqobat muhitiga ta'siri	325
Luqmanov Sharifxon A'zam o'g'li	
Logistika axborot tizimlarini texnologik jarayonlarga joriy etish.....	330
Uzaqov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
Принципы перехода к «Зелёной экономике» в Республике Узбекистан.....	336
Хамракулова Сусанна Тотуховна	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirish iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini prognozlash modellarini qo'llash	340
Ibragimova Gulchexra Toxirovna	
Raqamli ta'lim sharoitida liderlikning yangi qirralari	357
Oqmullaev Ravshan Raximjon o'g'li, Xodjievna Durdona Abdurasulovna	
Методология развития экологического менеджмента в промышленном хозяйстве выбросы в атмосферный воздух на горнодобывающих и металлургических предприятиях.....	361
Muradov Botir Xayat	
Strategik budjetlashtirish tizimining natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish tizimi bilan bog'liqligi, xalqaro tajriba va O'zbekiston uchun tavsiyalar	370
Xushmurotov Zoyir Bektemirovich	
Cultural branding and the entry of traditional products into the international market.....	374
Zebiniso Ganiyeva	
Farovonlikni baholash bo'yicha ilg'or xorijiy nazariy yondashuvlar	379
Norqobilov Nusratilla Norsaitovich	
O'zbekistonda hududlarini turizm salohiyatini innovatsion yondashuv asosida baholash	384
Umirova Dilnoza Safarovna	
Tourism education for sustainability: curriculum development in universities of Uzbekistan	393
Temirova Durdona, Yorqulov Muhammadmurod	
The contribution of small enterprises and private entrepreneurs to job creation in the labor market.....	399
Juraboev Haliljon	
Iqtisodiy o'sish sharoitida transport infratuzilmasi holati va uni rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	404
Haydarov Jahongir Aktamovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini moliyalashtirishni strategik boshqarishning nazariy asoslari va xorijiy tajribalar	410
Quvondiqov Farrux Ibragimovich	
Tijorat banklarida iqtisodiy samaradorlikni axborot texnologiyalar orqali rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	418
Dadenova Gulxan Kenesbaevna	
Механизмы совершенствования процедур выявления и анализа недостоверной финансовой отчетности в условиях учетной практики Узбекистана	422
Намозов Жасурбек Кувадович	
Влияние цифровых инструментов управления финансами на эффективность использования финансовых ресурсов	428
Хазираткулов Собиржон	

На пути к промышленному росту: опыт развивающихся стран.....	435
Matlyubov Xurshid Jamshidovich	
Yoshlarning moliyaviy mustaqilligiga erishishida aksiyalar bozorining oʻrni va imkoniyatlari.....	443
Oʻraqov Bekzodbek Abdurayxon oʻgʻli	
Развитие транспортной инфраструктуры и влияние на качество предоставляемых транспортных услуг.....	448
Kayyibekov Paraxat Konysbaevich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida 2015-2024 yillar mobaynida oziq-ovqat chakana savdo aylanmasining statistik tahlili	454
Toshpulatov Bobur Rasul oʻgʻli	
Qishloq xoʻjaligi sohasi investitsiya loyihalarini xalqaro moliya institutlari orqali moliyalashtirish.....	458
Tolibov Shoxrux Muminovich	
Qishloq xoʻjaligi korxonalarida buxgalteriya hisobining xususiyatlari va muammolari	463
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy oʻgʻli	
Institutional innovation and regional governance for balanced interregional cooperation development: the case of Namangan, Uzbekistan	468
Sattarov R.A.	
Organizational and economic mechanisms and conceptual directions of tourism development in the region.....	476
Daminova Barno Esanovna	

Daminova Barno Esanovna

Associate Professor, Karshi State University,

ORCID ID: 0009-0001-4211-6082

Email: barnod@mail.ru

ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS AND CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION

Abstract: This article analyzes the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of the tourism sector in the regions and develops conceptual directions that serve its sustainable development. Particular attention is paid to the modernization of tourism infrastructure, attracting investments, public-private partnerships, local brands and the development of ecological tourism. The need to develop regional tourism strategies based on territorial characteristics, existing tourist resources, demographic factors and economic opportunities is substantiated.

Key words: tourism, regional development, organizational and economic mechanisms, sustainable tourism, public-private partnerships, ecological tourism, infrastructure, innovation, investment, tourist brand.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mintaqalarda turizm sohasini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy va iqtisodiy mexanizmlari tahlil qilinib, uning barqaror rivojlanishiga xizmat qiluvchi konseptual yo'nalishlar ishlab chiqilgan. Turizm infratuzilmasini modernizatsiyalash, investitsiyalarni jalb etish, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, mahalliy brendlar va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Hududiy xususiyatlar, mavjud turistik resurslar, demografik omillar va iqtisodiy imkoniyatlar asosida hududiy turizm strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish zarurligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, mintaqaviy rivojlanish, tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlar, barqaror turizm, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, ekologik turizm, infratuzilma, innovatsiya, investitsiya, turistik brend.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются организационно-экономические механизмы развития сферы туризма в регионах и разрабатываются концептуальные направления, обеспечивающие ее устойчивое развитие. Особое внимание уделяется модернизации туристической инфраструктуры, привлечению инвестиций, государственно-частному партнерству, развитию локальных брендов и экотуризму. Обоснована необходимость разработки региональных стратегий развития туризма с учетом региональных особенностей, имеющихся туристических ресурсов, демографических факторов и экономических возможностей.

Ключевые слова: туризм, региональное развитие, организационно-экономические механизмы, устойчивый туризм, государственно-частное партнерство, экологический туризм, инфраструктура, инновации, инвестиции, туристический бренд.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan has become one of the priority areas of the national economy. In particular, through tourism there are opportunities to increase regional economic activity, create new jobs and expand export potential. In this regard, the correct formation and effective application of organizational and economic mechanisms aimed at developing the tourism sector is an urgent task.

Today, against the backdrop of global economic crises, the tourism industry is becoming a source of sustainable production. Regional tourism is an important tool for diversifying the economy based on local resources, creating jobs and promoting socio-economic development of regions.

The article aims to identify organizational and economic mechanisms for promoting tourism in regions and increasing competitiveness, linking them with practical prospects, and forming their conceptual basis.

Tourism is currently one of the fastest growing sectors of global economic growth. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), tourism accounts for about 10 percent of global GDP. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, tourism is recognized as one of the priority sectors in the national economy, and realizing the tourism potential, especially in the regions, has become an urgent task.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

International and local sources are equally important in the scientific study of tourism. Below is a review based on the literature related to the content of the article.

Butler's life cycle model of tourist areas [1], one of the international tourism theories, allows for the gradual development of regional tourism, resource management and assessment of crisis risks. This model served as the theoretical basis for the section on organizational development approaches of the article.

The work "The Geography of Tourism and Recreation" [2] developed by Hall and Page provides an in-depth analysis of the interrelationships of tourism geography, environmental factors and regional resources, and was used as the main source in the section on regional potential assessment in the article.

The manual "Tourism: Principles and Practice" [3] written by Cooper and co-authors reflects theoretical and practical approaches to the organization of modern tourism, service quality and marketing policy. This work served as the main source in the section on service quality and personnel training of the article.

In the analysis of tourism planning and policy, the impact of state policy on regional tourism was analyzed through the works of Dredge and Jenkins [4].

The strategy for the development of tourism at the state level in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular the Presidential Decree [5], defines the regulatory and legal framework for the concept of regional tourism. Also, practical mechanisms for financing infrastructure projects in the regions and establishing public-private partnerships are substantiated through the resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers [9].

The current state of tourism, tourist flows, the number of services and investment growth rates are presented in the statistical bulletins of the Tourism Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Statistics Committee [6], [14].

Of the works written by local authors, the scientific works of Kadyrov and Abdurakhmanov [7] served as the main source for the economic analysis of regional tourism, the cluster approach and the definition of investment mechanisms.

Tursunov and Azizov [8] also expressed relevant views on innovative tourism, digital technologies, AR/VR systems and online services. This approach is widely reflected in the sections of the article "Smart-tourism" and "Digital transformation".

Ziyodullayev [13] analyzed the theories of ecological tourism and sustainable development, and the concepts related to ecological directions in the article are based on this source.

Based on reports published by international organizations, including UNWTO [10], World Bank [11] and OECD [15], the article covers global tourism growth trends, the impact of state policy on tourism, changes during the pandemic and issues of environmental sustainability.

Karimov's work "Regional Economy and Tourism Clusters" [12] sheds light on the economic foundations of the formation of tourism clusters in the regions of Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is important to identify and propose effective organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of tourism in the regions, and to align them with conceptual development directions.

Tourism development is theoretically based on several schools:

- Butler model (1980) - tourism development is analyzed as a phased process (discovery, development, saturation, crisis or renewal).
- Endogenous growth theory - growth based on internal resources and innovations.
- Principles of sustainable development - an approach aimed at ensuring ecological, economic and social balance.

Local literature (I. Abdurahmonov, A. Jo'rayev, S. Karimov) covers issues of regional tourism strategies, brand creation and infrastructure development, while international sources (D. Hall, C. Cooper) focus on digital innovations and public-private partnership mechanisms in tourism.

Reports prepared by UNWTO (2022) and OECD (2020) provide the most up-to-date information on international trends, digital technologies, sustainable tourism policies, and the impact of public policies on

tourism. In particular, developments in the tourism sector in the post-pandemic period are highlighted based on these sources.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The tourism potential of such regions as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva - cultural and historical tourism centers, the Fergana Valley - handicraft and agro-tourism, Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya - archaeological and ecological tourism, Karakalpakstan - ethnotourism and ecological destinations (Aral Sea Coast) can be considered. The main problems are insufficient tourism infrastructure, shortage of qualified personnel, weak marketing strategy, limited investment environment, and weak interregional integration.

We will consider organizational and economic mechanisms and their role in development. Among them, public-private partnerships (PPP), the construction of hotels, roads and service facilities on a PPP basis, attracting private investors through tax incentives and grants, the proposal to establish a "Tourism Projects Fund". In addition, investment mechanisms, namely, attracting external investments: through EBRD, UNDP, OIC funds, internal investments: Tourism bonds, attracting local residents through cooperatives, the establishment of "Free Economic Zones for Tourism", Infrastructure modernization, namely, upgrading airports and railway stations, introducing environmentally friendly means of transport (electric buses), expanding Internet coverage and information centers.

We will look at the conceptual directions, namely, sustainable tourism, that is, reducing the negative impact of tourism activities on the environment, developing eco-hotels in rural areas, promoting the consumption of local products, Smart-tourism and digital transformation.

That is, virtual tours using AR/VR technologies, development of online booking systems, "Digital Guide" applications, mobile services. In addition, it is necessary to take into account personnel training and service quality, the establishment of regional tourism colleges, short courses on language learning and service culture, cooperation with international hotel chains, etc.

In the development of tourism in the regions, the geographical location of the territory, natural and climatic conditions, historical and cultural heritage and the state of existing infrastructure are considered the main factors. Each region has its own unique tourism resources, and economic growth can be achieved by studying and effectively managing them.

For example, in historical cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand and Khiva, tourism potential can be increased by preserving cultural heritage sites and combining them with modern services. In mountainous regions, the development of ecological and extreme types of tourism is promising.

For the main directions of forming organizational and economic mechanisms, the following organizational and economic mechanisms play an important role in the development of the tourism sector: projects based on public-private partnership, i.e., strengthening the participation of the private sector in the construction and modernization of tourism facilities, introducing state subsidies and tax incentives in the development of tourism infrastructure (roads, hotels, transport system), Attracting investments, i.e., strengthening the material and technical base of the tourism sector by attracting foreign and domestic investments, creating a favorable business environment for investors, Developing local brands and products, i.e., creating a tourist brand in each region, exporting local crafts and food products to international markets, Introducing innovative technologies, i.e., improving service provision through digital marketing, online booking systems, mobile applications, and gradually introducing the concept of "Smart tourism" at the regional level.

We will consider conceptual directions and strategic approaches. In the development of regional tourism, the following conceptual directions are considered priority: sustainable tourism, the development of forms of tourism that bring long-term economic benefits without harming the environment, Ecological tourism, the establishment of environmentally friendly tourism activities in mountainous and natural resource-rich regions, Agrotourism, attracting the population to tourism activities through the development of tourism related to agriculture, Education and training, that is, the development of a system of training specialized personnel in the tourism sector, teaching foreign languages, and improving service culture.

Several proposals can be made for the development of a regional tourism strategy. Among them, conducting a SWOT analysis of tourism potential in each region, encouraging the participation of local residents in tourism, developing tourist logistics - ensuring the convenience of air, rail and highways, developing a regional marketing strategy, and targeting foreign markets.

Tourism, as an important branch of the regional economy, has great potential in our country. For its effective development, it is necessary to properly form organizational and economic mechanisms, develop strategies taking into account regional characteristics. Innovations, approaches based on the principles of public-private partnership and sustainable development serve as important factors in this direction.

An integrated approach is required for the development of regional tourism. Taking into account the specific tourist potential of each region, it is necessary to develop organizational and economic mechanisms and correctly apply them in practice. Development based on sustainability, innovation, and public-private partnership is the basis of successful strategies.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the sustainable development of tourism in the region requires a coherent organizational and economic mechanism that integrates institutional coordination, public-private partnerships, infrastructure investment, and effective governance. A comprehensive regional tourism strategy should be built on the principles of inclusivity, diversification of tourism products, digital transformation, and environmental sustainability. Strengthening local capacities, enhancing service quality, and facilitating access to financial resources for small and medium-sized enterprises are essential to unlocking the full potential of the sector.

To further advance regional tourism, it is important to create an enabling environment through regulatory reforms, transparent policy frameworks, and active stakeholder engagement. Special attention should be paid to promoting local cultural and natural assets, fostering innovation in tourism services, and improving transport and communication infrastructure. Additionally, the implementation of destination branding and targeted marketing campaigns can significantly enhance the region's visibility in both domestic and international markets, attracting more visitors and boosting socio-economic development.

List of used literature:

- Butler, R. W. (1980). The concept of a tourist area cycle of evolution: Implications for management of resources. *Canadian Geographer*, 24(1), 5–12.
- Hall, C. M., & Page, S. J. (2014). *The Geography of Tourism and Recreation: Environment, Place and Space*. Routledge.
- Cooper, C., Fletcher, J., Fyall, A., Gilbert, D., & Wanhill, S. (2008). *Tourism: Principles and Practice*. Pearson Education.
- Dredge, D., & Jenkins, J. (2007). *Tourism Planning and Policy*. John Wiley & Sons.
- O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 5-yanvardagi PF-5611-sonli Farmoni – “2019–2025 yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasida turizm sohasini rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi to'g'risida”.
- O'zbekiston Respublikasi Turizmni rivojlantirish davlat qo'mitasi. Statistik axborotlar byulleteni (2023–2024 yillar).
- Qodirov, A., & Abdurahmonov, I. (2020). *Turizmni rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy asoslari*. Toshkent: Iqtisodiyot nashriyoti.
- Tursunov, B. O., & Azizov, S. I. (2021). Hududiy turizmni rivojlantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar. // “Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar” jurnali, №6.
- O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2021-yil 25-noyabrdagi 723-son qarori – “Hududlarda turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirish dasturi”.
- UNWTO (2022). *International Tourism Highlights: 2022 Edition*. World Tourism Organization.
- World Bank (2023). *Tourism for Development: A Pathway to Sustainable Growth – The World Bank Group Report*.
- Karimov, S. T. (2019). *Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot va turizm klasterlari*. – Toshkent: “Fan va taraqqiyot” nashriyoti.
- Ziyodullayev, N. (2021). *Ekoturizmni rivojlantirishning konseptual asoslari*. // “Innovatsion iqtisodiyot va menejment” ilmiy jurnali, №3.
- State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics (2024). *Tourism Indicators Report*. www.stat.uz
- OECD (2020). *OECD Tourism Trends and Policies 2020*. Paris: OECD Publishing.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 7

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>